

Perceptual Masking and Cochlear Suppression Measured using Frequency Sweeps

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Abstract. Human behavioral studies have shown that upward and downward sweeps can produce substantially different masked thresholds of a tonal signal, where upsweeps are more effective at masking the tone compared to downsweeps. The behavioral literature attributes the dependence on sweep direction to cochlear dispersion (phase curvature), which involves variations in the shape of the basilar membrane (BM) waveform generated by each masker at the signal frequency place. Although animal measurements and physiological models support this interpretation, recent measurements of cochlear vibration in mouse also reveal differences in the cochlear suppression produced by up-vs-down swept suppressors, and these differences are dependent on sweep rate (Charaziak, 2022). These findings suggest that the differences in the processing of up-vs-down sweep stimuli, such as in up-vs-downswept behavioral masking, may also be related to suppression. If the mechanism for the differences in up-vs-down behavioral masking and suppression are both related to cochlear dispersion, their dependence on sweep rate and direction should be similar. Suppression can be studied in humans indirectly and non-invasively using otoacoustic emissions (OAE). In the current study, we measured behavioral masking and the magnitude of stimulus-frequency OAE (SFOAE) residuals as a function of sweep rate and direction in normal hearing humans at ~1 and ~4 kHz signal/probe frequencies. We used linear frequency sweeps in both the behavioral masking and SFOAE experiments, either as maskers or suppressors, respectively. Consistent with the sweep direction effects in the behavioral masking literature, the upward sweeps were more effective maskers/suppressors than downward sweeps. Interestingly, we found that the dependence on sweep rate was nonmonotonic, with the largest up-down differences in both behavioral masking and OAE suppression occurring at sweep rates similar to otoacoustic estimates of the group velocity of the cochlear traveling wave. These preliminary findings suggest that up-vs-down swept behavioral masking and OAE suppression share common generation mechanisms, presumably closely related to mechanical suppression in the cochlea.

INTRODUCTION

Classic human perceptual studies using “Schroeder-phase complexes” have linked behavioral masking to cochlear processes. Schroeder-phase stimuli contain multiple harmonic frequency components of equal magnitude but variable starting phase, summing to produce a series of periodic frequency sweeps [1]. Behavioral studies find that negative Schroeder-phase maskers (i.e., upward sweeps; from low-to-high frequency) are more effective maskers of tonal signals than positive Schroeder-phase maskers (i.e., downward sweeps; from high-to-low frequency) with differences reaching 20 dB in some cases [2, 3]. The behavioral literature on Schroeder-phase masking interprets the dependence on sweep direction as arising primarily from cochlear dispersion (phase curvature), which creates modulations in the envelope of the basilar membrane (BM) waveform generated by each periodic masker. Due to dispersion, the BM waveform for the downsweep is “peakier” compared to the broader response of the upsweep. Consequently, the presence of a downswept masker allows for easier detection of the signal in the dips of its waveform. This interpretation has found support in animal measurements [4, 5] and physiological models [2, 3, 6]. While dispersion has been used to explain the up-vs-down masking effects, recent measurements of cochlear vibration in mouse also reveal differences in the cochlear suppression produced by up-vs-down swept suppressors, and these differences are dependent on sweep rate [7]. Cochlear suppression (e.g., two-tone suppression) is a nonlinear property

in the cochlea in which there is a reduction in the response to one tone in the presence of another [8]. At fast sweep rates, the results from Charaziak [7] showed significant differences in BM suppression depending on suppressor direction (up-vs-down), but the slow rates showed little difference. These findings suggest that the differences in the processing of up-vs-down sweep stimuli, such as in behavioral Schroeder-phase masking, may also be related to suppression. Similar physiological measures of suppression using up-and-downswept stimuli for a wide range of sweep rates have not been conducted with humans, nor have suppression effects been compared to behavioral masking.

We hypothesized that if behavioral Schroeder-phase masking and suppression are both related to cochlear dispersion, their dependence on sweep rate and direction should be similar. Suppression can be indirectly and noninvasively studied in humans using otoacoustic emissions (OAE). In the current study, we measured behavioral masking and the magnitude of stimulus-frequency OAE (SFOAE) residuals as a function of sweep rate and direction in normal hearing humans at ~ 1 and ~ 4 kHz signal/probe frequencies. We used linear frequency sweeps in both the behavioral masking and SFOAE experiments, either as maskers or suppressors, respectively. Linear frequency sweeps are similar to Schroeder-phase stimuli but allow better control of the temporal and spectral properties.

METHODS

Subjects – Audiological Screening and Pretesting

Seven normal-hearing subjects (3 male and 4 female) participated in the experiments. Their ages ranged from 31 to 38 (median = 34 years). All subjects met the screening criteria for the study: all audiometric thresholds from 250 – 8000 Hz \leq than 15 dB HL, normal middle-ear function (type A tympanograms). A pretesting SFOAE test was conducted to determine if emissions were present over a wide frequency range (500 Hz – 16 kHz), where present SFOAEs required a minimum criterion of 6 dB signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) when binned over $\frac{1}{2}$ octave bands centered at the probe frequency. This was done using a 40 dB FPL probe tone and a suppressor at 60 dB FPL, and repeated (approximately 30–64 repetitions) until the criteria SNR was achieved. Subjects were required to have present SFOAEs from 750 Hz – 6 kHz to qualify for the study. Next, a brief test was conducted for detection of spontaneous otoacoustic emissions (SOAE) in the test ear. The resulting spectra of the SFOAE and SOAE tests guided the selection of the signal/probe frequencies used in our experiments, with 1 and 4 kHz being the frequencies of interest. We selected a subject's signal/probe frequencies based on the largest SFOAE spectral peak within 500 Hz of 1 and 4 kHz, requiring that it be at least 250 Hz away from any SOAE. Participants provided consent before pretesting and were monetarily reimbursed. All testing met the guidelines of the Institutional Review Board at the University of Southern California.

Behavioral Stimuli and Methods

The behavioral experiment was conducted to determine the dependence of sweep rate and direction using linear frequency sweeps as maskers of a tonal signal. The signals were ~ 1 and ~ 4 kHz pure tones and were 120 ms in duration, including 10-ms rise/fall times shaped with a Blackman-window. These signal frequencies (f_s) are far enough apart to test both lower and higher frequency regions of the human cochlea, and these f_s have been used in previous studies to study frequency effects in Schroeder-phase masking [9]. The masker was 480 ms in duration, including 10-ms rise/fall times shaped with a Blackman-window. It consisted of multiple, concatenated periodic linear frequency sweeps of specified rate created in the time domain. Sweeps of different rates differ in the spacing of their harmonic components. Sweep bandwidths incorporated spanned frequency components between $0.4f_s$ and $1.6f_s$, thereby keeping the masker bandwidth frequency ratio the same for each f_s . The signal was temporally centered within the masker (Fig. 1A). Also, the phase of the signal was equal to the phase of the masker frequency component of the same frequency. Masker sweep rates ranged from 3.6 to 361.3 oct/s, and glided upwards or downwards with frequency. In all behavioral tasks [i.e., quiet threshold of the signal (signal alone), and masking threshold (signal + masker)], the stimuli were presented in the presence of a low intensity notched noise (20 dB RMS re signal quiet threshold). Notched noise was used to limit off-frequency listening and restrict listening to the auditory filter corresponding to the signal frequency. Notched noise was 480 ms in duration, including 10-ms rise/fall times (shaped with a Blackman-window). Notch-noise bandwidth spanned ~ 10 Hz–20 kHz, with low and high notch cutoff-frequencies of $0.4f_s$ and $1.6f_s$, respectively. Therefore, there was no spectral overlap between the masker's frequency components and the notched noise.

First, subjects started with a quiet threshold task of the signal. Then, for the behavioral masking task, the signal was fixed at 20 dB sensation level (SL), and the masker level was adjusted to find the level needed to just mask the

signal (Fig 1A). The signal's sensation level was chosen to be high enough to measure the dynamic range of masking thresholds for the up-and-down frequency sweeps. We analyzed the differences in up-vs-down swept behavioral masking thresholds as a function of masker sweep rate (Fig. 2A & 2B). Masker sweep/rate direction combinations were tested in random order. Masked thresholds from this task provide the response to the signal in the presence of the dynamic frequency sweeps. All behavioral measures were completed in a double-walled sound-attenuating booth and conducted on a testing laptop. Behavioral testing was conducted with a psychoacoustic software package [10], using custom MATLAB (MathWorks, Inc., Natick, MA) software to digitally generate the stimuli. Stimuli were converted to analog using a Babyface Pro USB High Speed Audio Interface (RME Audio, Germany), and then delivered to Sennheiser HD 280 Pro headphones. The software utilized a three-alternative forced-choice tracking procedure which estimates the 70.7% correct point on the psychometric function [11]. The inter-stimulus interval in these behavioral tasks was 500 ms (Fig 1A, gray bars). Subjects used a mouse or keyboard to select the interval containing the signal. Visual feedback was given for correct/incorrect responses.

Otoacoustic Stimuli and Methods

The SFOAE suppression experiment was conducted to obtain a non-invasive physiological measure of suppression at specific regions of the cochlea in response to linear frequency swept suppressors varying in sweep rate and direction. A modified interleaved suppression method [12] was used to extract the SFOAEs using tonal probe stimuli to evoke the response and linear frequency sweeps as the suppressors. The SFOAE stimuli were kept as similar as possible to the behavioral stimuli. The probe frequencies (f_p) used were identical to the f_s used in the behavioral experiment (~1 and ~4 kHz) determined by the pretesting procedure. One difference between the SFOAE probe and the behavioral signal is that the probe's duration was 432 ms, while the behavioral signal was shorter in duration (120 ms). The longer probe duration was used to reduce the overall measurement time and provide an overall response with a high signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The SFOAE suppressors were generated the same way as the behavioral maskers (see Behavioral Stimuli & Methods), and were identical to them in terms of: (A) the sweep rate/direction combinations used, (B) the overall duration, (C) and their frequency components. The level of the probe was 40 dB forward-pressure level (FPL) and the suppressor was 60 dB FPL.

The responses to four stimulus combinations were collected: p_1 = probe tone alone, p_2 = probe and suppressor tone (+polarity), p_3 = probe tone alone, and p_4 = probe and suppressor tone (-polarity). In this sequence, the suppressor either has a positive or negative polarity so that adding the responses to the probe + suppressors condition cancels the suppressors (see Fig. 1B). The difference between the two conditions results in the overall SFOAE time waveform, and was calculated using the formula: $p_{\text{SFOAE}} = (p_1 - p_2 + p_3 - p_4)/2$. The magnitude and phase of the residual SFOAE at the probe frequency was estimated using a least-squares fitting procedure [13]. The residual was computed over the entire time course of the probe. The extracted SFOAE provides a measure of suppression at the probe frequency. A total of 64 repetitions of this probe and suppressor sequence were collected for each sweep rate/direction combination, and these combinations were presented in random order. Artifacts were identified by analyzing the time waveform of the residual. Any outliers were rejected and removed from the average. Uncertainties (error bars) were estimated by resampling. We analyzed the amplitude ratio of up-vs-down swept SFOAE residuals as a function of suppressor sweep

FIGURE 1. Schematic time-waveforms of the (A) behavioral and (B) SFOAE stimuli used. (A) The signal (red) was fixed at 20 dB SL and the level of the masker (blue) was tracked for each masker sweep/direction combination. The difference in masking threshold for up-and-down sweeps were analyzed for each masker sweep rate. (B) The ear-canal pressure for the probe alone condition (red) served as the baseline condition and was compared to the ear-canal pressure for a condition where the probe and suppressor were presented together (blue). SFOAE-residual amplitude ratios for up-and-down swept suppressors were analyzed for each suppressor sweep rate. The example illustrated here shows three periods (upsweep) of the masker (A) and suppressor (B).

rate (Fig. 2C & 2D). These SFOAE suppression measures are analogous to the BM suppression measurements made in mouse [7].

Stimulus generation and SFOAE acquisition were controlled using custom MATLAB (MathWorks, Inc., Natick, MA) software on a testing laptop and ER-10X probe system (Elk Grove Village, IL). Digital stimuli were converted to analog voltage using a Babyface Pro USB High Speed Audio Interface (RME Audio, Germany), converted to an analog signal, and delivered to the ER-10X probe. The ER-10X system utilizes FPL stimulus calibrations to correct for the effects of standing waves of the ear canal [14]. For details of ER-10X probe and in-ear subject calibration used in our experiments, see [15]. SFOAE testing was completed in a double-walled sound-attenuating booth where subjects were reclined in a comfortable chair during testing. After hardware and probe calibration, subjects were instructed to watch a subtitled video of their choice while sitting as still as possible.

RESULTS

Differences in up-vs-down swept behavioral masking thresholds as a function of masker sweep rate are shown in Fig. 2A ($f_s = \sim 1$ kHz) and Fig. 2B ($f_s = \sim 4$ kHz), respectively. The horizontal dotted line at zero indicates no difference in up-vs-down swept masking level. Two subjects completed the behavioral experiment at both 1 and 4 kHz f_s (S1 & S7). Individual subject data are shown in thin tracings and the average data are shown in thick tracings (blue). Upsweeps were stronger maskers than downsweeps in nearly all cases (i.e., above the horizontal line). Both up-vs-down masking curves at 1 and 4 kHz are nonmonotonic (bell-shaped). For 1 kHz, large up-vs-down masking differences (5 – 8 dB) were found at all sweep rates except for the slowest and fastest rates. In contrast, for 4 kHz, the up-vs-down masking difference peak is larger (~ 11 dB) and is shifted rightward to faster rates. The largest differences occurred around ~ 40 oct/s (ranging 30 – 70 oct/s) at 1 kHz and ~ 80 oct/s (50 – 120 oct/s) at 4 kHz.

SFOAE residual amplitude ratios between up/down linear sweeps as a function of suppressor sweep rate are shown in Fig. 2C ($f_p = \sim 1$ kHz) and Fig. 2D ($f_p = \sim 4$ kHz), respectively. Six subjects completed the SFOAE experiment at $f_p = \sim 1$ kHz (S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S7) and five subjects completed the experiment at $f_p = \sim 4$ kHz (S1, S2, S3, S6, S7). The dotted line at zero indicates no difference in up-vs-down SFOAE residual amplitude. Individual data are shown in thin tracings and the average data shown in thick tracings (red). Similar to our behavioral data, upsweeps were stronger suppressors than downsweeps (i.e., above the horizontal line). Both 1 and 4 kHz data show bell-shaped patterns, also similar to the behavioral data. For 1 kHz, the SFOAE difference peaks (~ 3 dB) at sweep rates near ~ 40 -50 oct/s. In contrast, for 4 kHz, the peak (~ 3 dB) is shifted rightward to the range of 90-120 oct/s. Overall, the qualitative pattern in the SFOAE suppression data coincide with the behavioral data for a given probe/signal frequency. While sharing similar sweep rate/direction dependencies, we note that the peak amplitude ratios of up/down SFOAE suppression effects were smaller in magnitude than the up-vs-down behavioral masking differences.

DISCUSSION

In the current study, we used linear frequency sweeps as maskers/suppressors and measured the effect of sweep rate and direction on behavioral masking and cochlear suppression at signal/probe frequencies of 1 and 4 kHz. In agreement with previous behavioral masking studies, we find that upsweeps were more effective maskers than downsweeps. Similarly, the upsweeps produced more cochlear suppression. The up-vs-down masking/suppression differences were nonmonotonic and bell-shaped as a function of sweep rate, but they differed in their peak locations (~ 40 -50 oct/s for 1 kHz, and ~ 80 -120 oct/s for 4 kHz).

To help understand the masker and suppressor rate/direction dependencies found in our data, we compared the sweep rates tested to the estimated velocity of the traveling wave near its peak in humans (Fig. 3). Traveling wave velocity was estimated from the SFOAE group delay [16], and is plotted by the black tracing along with its uncertainty band ($\pm 30\%$) as a function of frequency [13]. Frequency (signal or probe) is plotted along the x -axis while sweep rate expressed in octaves/s is plotted along the y -axis. Physiological and modeling data have shown that the gliding of frequency sweeps on the basilar membrane is closely related to cochlear traveling-wave dispersion [17]. The group velocity of the cochlear traveling wave has been used to distinguish “fast” from “slow” sweep rates [13]. Sweep rates well above the line produce ‘transient’ (i.e., click-like) stimuli whose instantaneous frequency components sweep along the BM faster than the traveling wave; sweep rates well below the line yield ‘steady-state’ (i.e., tonal) stimuli whose excitation pattern moves more slowly than the traveling-wave velocity. The magenta star and error bars indicate the mean and range of rates tested at the 1 and 4 kHz regions. At both frequencies tested, the up-vs-down masking/suppression curves peak at values close to the estimated group velocity of the traveling wave, approximately

~50 oct/s for 1 kHz and ~100 oct/s for 4 kHz, suggesting that this velocity is a key factor determining how the cochlea responds to sound. While more data are needed, the similar dependence on sweep rate suggests that both behavioral masking and OAE suppression share common mechanisms, presumably closely related to mechanical suppression in the cochlea.

FIGURE 2. The differences in up-vs-down behavioral masking (A & B) and amplitude ratio for up/down SFOAE suppression (C & D) produce bell-shaped functions. Thick tracings (blue = behavior; red = SFOAE) in each panel represent the averaged data while thin tracings are individual subject data. Data for 1 kHz are aligned vertically to the left and data for 4 kHz are aligned vertically to the right. The peak differences in masking/suppression occur at ~40-50 oct/s at 1 kHz, and 80-120 oct/s at 4 kHz.

FIGURE 3. The group velocity of the cochlear traveling wave distinguishes fast (click-like; transient) and slow (tonal; steady-state) sweeps. The thick black line (with its estimated uncertainty) represents the velocity of the traveling wave at its peak (in oct/s) derived from SFOAE group delay [see (13)]. The x-axis gives signal (or probe) frequency and the y-axis gives sweep rate. The dashed vertical bars indicate the range of sweep rates tested. Interestingly, the peak differences in up-vs-downswept masking/suppression are well predicted by the group velocity of the traveling wave, ~50 oct/s at 1 kHz and ~100 oct/s at 4 kHz. Figure adapted from [13].

Some future directions of our work include using different types of frequency sweeps in our behavioral and SFOAE suppression experiments, including Schroeder-phase complexes and exponential frequency sweeps. Periodic linear frequency sweeps were used in the current study, and it is not clear if differences in masking/suppression would occur with these alternative sweeps, where their frequency components as well as the slope of their frequency glide

may differ. We also want to test for intra-subject correlation, where the peak difference in up-vs-down SFOAE suppression predicts the peak in up-vs-down behavioral masking. While the overall bell-shaped pattern occurs for our individual subjects, inter-subject variability exists in our data, and we want to better understand this occurrence. On that end, more subjects should be tested in our experiments. Considering the findings in the current study, Charaziak made further recordings of BM suppression, but using a larger range of suppressor sweep rates in mice than in her prior work [7]. In agreement with our human data, her latest findings show similar bell-shaped patterns that peak approximately at the rate of dispersion for the f_p tested [see Charaziak, in this volume (18)]. Our data, as well as mouse BM data [7], suggest that the differences in up-vs-down masking depend not only on cochlear dispersion but also on the interaction between suppression and dispersion. Nonlinear cochlear models will provide further insights into the underlying mechanisms. Although cochlear suppression has long been studied using static stimuli (i.e., tones), our human data and mouse data [7] support the idea that the temporal aspects of cochlear suppression need to be better understood, both on a mechanistic level as well as for their possible ecological relevance to perception.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

Václav Vencovský: Your idea of comparing SFOAEs and behavioral masking thresholds is great because SFOAEs tell us which signal is available in the cochlea and causes OAE generation. In addition, masking thresholds tell whether these vibrations can be perceived. For the masking experiment, you use a 20 dB SL tone and change the masker intensity to find the masking threshold. For the SFOAE experiment, the masker is 60 dB FPL and probe tone is 40 dB FPL. You only present differences in the masking thresholds, so it is not possible to see how much the masker levels and suppressor levels differ. The masking effect of Schroeder-phase complexes is level dependent, which may complicate comparing OAEs and behavioral masking results in your study (Shen and Lentz, *J Acoust Soc Am* 126:2501–2510, 2009). Schroeder-phase complexes are usually generated with constant fundamental frequency, equal amplitude of spectral components and variable phase. The phase determines the sweep direction and rate. If I understand it correctly, you generate swept sines and present them repeatedly and the fundamental frequency of such created signal depends on the sweep rate. Therefore, the amount of suppression and masking should also depend on the amplitude spectrum of these swept sines. Is this correct? However, the upward and downward-swept stimuli will have the same amplitude spectrum.

Will Salloom: Thank you for the feedback; you bring up interesting points. There are inherent differences between the fixed-level stimuli used in the SFOAE suppression experiment and the stimulus levels used in the behavioral experiment. The probe in the SFOAE experiment was 40 dB FPL, and the signal level in the behavioral experiment was fixed at 20 dB SL. These are both relatively low intensities and were chosen to avoid other types of peripheral effects (MOC and MEM efferent activity) and because two-tone suppression itself is intensity dependent. Also, the level of the signal we chose was based on the large dynamic range needed to track masking thresholds, which can be very large between up-vs-down swept masking. While the signal and probe may not be perfectly matched in level, we aimed for the signal/probe to be on the lower portion of the cochlear input/output function. We find that our behavioral and SFOAE results are very similar qualitatively (bell-shaped) and both share similar masking/suppression direction and rate dependencies, at least with the preliminary data that we collected. For future work, we could fix the SFOAE probe levels to match the SL used in the behavioral experiment for each subject and verify our results. We could also fix the masker's intensity to match the suppressor's intensity and track the signal threshold, as other studies have done. Alternatively, we could do an iso-response suppression OAE experiment that mirrors our behavioral experiment by adjusting the level of the suppressors until you get the specified level of suppression (i.e., OAE residual). Lastly, we are interested in testing sweep direction/rate effects at different stimulus intensities in future work.

The answer is yes regarding your question on how our linear frequency sweeps were generated, and also on the influence of the amplitude of the sweep components on masking/suppression effectiveness. The sweep rate was determined by the number of repetitions of the masker/suppressor stimuli within a 480 ms total duration. Increasing the number of repetitions increases the f_0 of the stimulus, as well as the sweep rate. As you point out, the up- and downsweeps share the same spectra, but the amount of masking they produce at the signal/probe frequency place will also be dependent on the amplitude of the components, especially components closest to the signal/probe frequency.

Stephen Neely: Have you considered running any of your swept-stimuli through a model? It would be interesting if you find any differences between the upsweeps and downsweeps in a model, particularly if there are any loudness differences. We have a cochlear model that takes different aspects of psychophysics into account to understand loudness perception that you may be interested in exploring with your maskers/suppressor stimuli.

Will Salloom: We are very interested in running our stimuli through a cochlear model. We could run some of our stimuli in your model, and to see if loudness differences exist between the up-and-downsweeps. In terms of loudness, there is a classic psychoacoustic (with some modeling) paper that discussed loudness perception and Schroeder-phase masking, [Carlyon & Datta. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* (1997); 101:6. Pages 3636–3647]. However, I do not think that there has been a whole lot of work done relating the up-vs-downswept Schroeder masking (or similar stimuli) to the percept of loudness specifically.

Uzma Akhtar: This is a really interesting approach for understanding cochlear mechanics and classic psychoacoustics. Just wondering what the variability you're seeing across subjects means in terms of cochlear status.

Given that these participants are still normal-hearing yet in their thirties, do you think this measure of cochlear processing (the up/down difference) could have some clinical utility for assessing subclinical dysfunction? Perhaps you could look at extended high frequency hearing in your participants to try to understand the variability better?

Will Salloom: That is an interesting question about the inter-subject variation in the sensitivity to up-vs-down masking/suppression and its possible interaction with age. There is psychoacoustic data to support that suppression decreases with age (Sommers & Gher; *Hear. Res.* 264:1-2. [2010], Pages 56-62). It is possible that the sweep rate/direction dependencies that we found in up-vs-down masking and suppression may differ with age as well (both in the range and peak sensitivity), and interesting hypothesis to test in future work. Further, there is psychoacoustic data to support that the up-vs-down swept masking differences decreases significantly with cochlear hearing loss (Summers & Leek; *Hear. Res.* 118:1-2. [1998], Pages 139-150). In future work, we would like to explore the sweep rate/direction dependencies of up-vs-down masking and suppression for individuals with cochlear hearing loss.

It is possible that sensitivity to up-vs-downswept sound plays a role in everyday listening, such as “listening in the dips” to complex sounds which rapidly fluctuate in frequency (i.e., speech and music) that may be masked by background noise. In terms of clinical or sub-clinical utility, it would be interesting to know how the impaired and/or aging auditory systems sensitivity to these swept sounds (masking/suppression) correlate to speech-in-noise tests. There exists a spectro-temporal test using rippled noise to infer speech-in-noise performance. It may be worth investigating in future work if some of our metrics for up-vs-down swept masking and suppression correlate to speech-in-noise performance, and if any observable relationship varies with age. As for extended high-frequency testing, we do want to try different signal/probe frequency combinations with our tasks to better understand how up-vs-down swept processing works in the auditory system.

Afagh Farhadi: Dear authors, I like the idea of combining SFOAE and behavioral measures to better understand cochlear masking. It is a great paper and I enjoyed reading it. I have several questions about your results. Do you think the results from the SFOAE experiment would differ from day-to-day, and have you done any variability testing yet? I was also wondering is there any way to collect both SFOAE and behavioral data simultaneously? Beyond the scope of this paper, what are some general limitations to the study? For your SFOAE experiment, I was wondering if it is possible to analyze phase information too since you only reported magnitude data? Would that be worth looking into to help understand the contributing factors to the effects you found, and to better understand the effect of cochlear dispersion versus suppression? One general comment I have is that it may be worth writing a few sentences about the bigger picture idea of why these swept stimuli are important to study. Perhaps one reason to study them is because of their similarity to speech, and understanding how swept sounds are processed could be related to the mechanisms of speech recognition in background noise?

Will Salloom: Thank you for the comments/questions. We have presented some replicability of our SFOAE data from a few subjects at the past ARO (Salloom et al., 2024; see Fig. 11), where the SFOAE task was conducted on separate days. The overall sensitivity to up-vs-down swept suppressors are replicated very well, both in terms of the effect size and the qualitative pattern of the SFOAE residuals due to the suppressors, at least with the conditions and subjects we tested. We could verify those results in a few more subjects for the full study. Next, it would be difficult to record the behavioral and SFOAE data at the same time as we don't want the subjects to move or interact while the otoacoustic measures are taking place. It would take a special configuration and testing paradigm to do so.

That is an interesting question about SFOAE phase information, as we have only presented our SFOAE magnitude results. Phase information could help us understand more about how the masker/suppressor is interacting at the signal/probe location. So yes, we think it would be worth looking at in the future. For a big picture perspective, it has been thought that the differences in up-vs-downswept masking may reflect a “listening in the dips” mechanism that facilitates signal detection in the presence of background noise. This mechanism is dependent on phase sensitivity in the auditory system as well as cochlear dispersion. However, Karolina Charaziak's data in mouse and our data in humans support that the up-vs-down swept masking effects are also linked to cochlear suppression, and should be further studied to better understand how these complex interactions in the cochlea ultimately influence perception.

Salloom, W.B, Shera, C.A., & Charaziak, K.K. (2024). Exploring Human Cochlear Masking and OAE Suppression at Different Cochlear Locations Using Frequency Sweeps. 47th Annual MidWinter Meeting - Association for Research in Otolaryngology (ARO), Anaheim, California. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12729238>